

EFFECT OF SIX MONTHS SURYANAMASKAR TRAINING ON SELECTED PHYSIOLOGICAL AND MOTOR FITNESS VARIABLES OF SCHOOL GOING STUDENTS OF DELHI

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to evaluate the impact of six months of regular Suryanamaskar exercise on motor fitness parameters of school-going students of Delhi. The project was aimed at investigating muscular strength, measured through standing broad jump test, and cardiovascular efficiency, measured through heart rate test. This was undertaken in light of the deteriorating level of physical fitness of youths due to their inactive lifestyle and low engagement in physical activities.

For the conduct of the experiment, an experimental research design involving a control group was used. A total of 40 school-going children of age group 13-16 years was chosen from Navyug School, Mandir Marg, New Delhi. The subjects were divided equally into two groups, namely the Experimental Group consisting of 20 children who were administered an organized Suryanamaskar training program, and the Control Group consisting of 20 children who continued to perform their school activities as usual. The Experimental Group was administered a six-month-long Suryanamaskar training program, while no special program was administered to the Control Group. The standing broad jump test and resting heart rate of both groups were taken at the pre-test stage (0 month) and post-test stage (6 month) through standard testing methods. The mean and standard deviation were calculated, and the significance of the differences in the scores obtained from the post-test and pre-test was analyzed through t-test on the 0.05 significance level.

Results obtained from the study made it obvious that there was a substantial improvement in the Experimental Group with regard to Standing Broad Jump and a reduction in resting heart rate after six months of Suryanamaskar exercise when compared to the Control Group. However, in the Control Group, there were no changes in Standing Broad Jump performance and resting heart rate. Based on the analysis, it has been concluded that the regular practice of Suryanamaskar exercises for a period of six months helps to develop the strength and cardiovascular efficiency of the students to a significant effect.

Keywords- Suryanamaskar, Standing Broad Jump, Resting Heart Rate, Motor Fitness, School-Going Students

Introduction

Physical fitness in adolescence is a crucial parameter in guaranteeing healthy growth and proper physiological functioning in a person. Muscular strength and cardiovascular efficiency are some of the important components of physical fitness, and lack of this component among school-going children has been observed to be on a significant declining trend in recent times, especially in urban areas like Delhi. The factors attributed to this lack of physical fitness in the youth include academic pressures, less playtime outside, and a sedentary lifestyle due to screen times and similar factors in their daily lives.

Muscular strength is a very imperative motor component that helps carry out everyday functions effectively, comprising the basics required for developing other motor skills. The standing broad jump test is very commonly utilized for measuring explosive muscular strength of legs, besides measuring the effective function of the lower limb musculature. Appropriate muscular strength in adolescence not only improves athletic performance but also provides support for postural stability and injury prevention. Inadequate muscular strength can impart negative effects on motor coordination and physical competence.

Heart rate when the organism is at rest is a significant physiological parameter of the efficiency of the cardiovascular system. An optimal heart rate is known to be lower, which is associated with efficient function of the heart along with higher circulatory efficiency. Engaging in organized physical activities has proved to be effective in optimizing heart rate by increasing stroke volume, which in turn decreases the workload of the heart. In adolescents, optimizing circulatory efficiency is critical to maintain physical activities.

Systematic and sustained opportunities to engage in physical exercise are not commonly available to students within the current school setting today. Physical exercises such as sports programs may need specialized equipment or even extensive hours of the school day, which may not be feasible to conduct given the time limitations of the school setting. Thus, the need to find interventions that are time-efficient and effective and that affect multiple aspects of fitness at once.

Suryanamaskar can be defined as a traditional Yoginiac practice that involves a series of twelve postures that need to be completed in a flowing rhythm. It combines dynamic body movements with regulated breathing processes. As such, it offers dual stimulation for the muscular-skeletal system together with the cardiovascular system. The exercise involves weight-bearing movements, both backward and forward bending, which may increase muscular strength and the efficacy of the cardiovascular system. Further, Suryanamaskar can be carried out with minimal equipment requirements and can be conducted anywhere, including the school environment.

Earlier studies that were carried out in the related domain of physical education and yoga sciences have generated positive results regarding the influence of yoga practices on diverse dimensions of physical fitness. However, a number of studies were performed on more than one variable or were carried out over a short term. The need still persists for specialized long-term research that concentrates on the impact of Suryanamaskar upon diverse variables related to school-going adolescents. The current study was thus conducted to assess the influence of six months of Suryanamaskar exercise training on the standing broad jump ability and heart rate of school-going children of Delhi. By using an experimental setup with a control group, an attempt will be made in this study to establish scientific evidence about the usefulness of Suryanamaskar exercise in increasing muscle power and cardiovascular ability of adolescents.

Methodology

The present investigation aimed at studying the impact of six months of systematic Suryanamaskar training on selected motor fitness and physiological variables, namely standing broad jump and resting heart rate, of school-going students of Delhi. The methodological procedures adopted in this study were strictly based on the framework described in the thesis and were structured in accordance with the format followed in standard physical education research.

Research Design

An experimental research design with a control group was used in the present study. Further, this design was found adequate and suitable to watch the effect of the Suryanamaskar training programme on the selected variables which are measured and compared in both Experimental and Control Groups over a continuous period of six months. Pre-test and post-test measurements were taken to evaluate changes due to intervention.

Selection of Subject

The subjects for the study were selected from Navyug School, Mandir Marg, New Delhi. For this study, a sample of 40 school-going students aged between 13 and 16 years were selected. The selected subjects were randomly assigned into two groups:

- Experimental Group: 20 Students
- Control Group: 20 students

The Experimental Group subjects underwent the Suryanamaskar training programme whereas the Control Group students continued their routine school activities without any extra training intervention.

Training Programme

The training program in Suryanamaskar was given to the Experimental Group in a systematic way for six months. The subjects were trained five days a week, with each session lasting about 45 minutes. The training program consisted of the systematic practice of the twelve postures of Suryanamaskar executed in a rhythmic sequence with coordinated breathing. The training load was progressively increased in due course to ensure progressive adaptation without allowing the onset of fatigue or injury. All the training programs were performed under proper supervision to maintain uniformity with correct execution of postures.

The Control Group did not participate in any Suryanamaskar training and followed their regular academic and physical education schedule as prescribed by the school.

Selection of Variables

The Suryanamaskar training programme was the independent variable of the study. The dependent variables selected for this study were as follows:

- Standing Broad Jump (Motor Fitness Component)
- Resting Heart Rate (Physiological Variable)

Criteria measures

- The selected variables were measured utilizing the following standardized tests and procedures:
- Standing Broad Jump: This test evaluated the muscular strength of the lower extremities. Distance jumped was measured in meters and recorded to the nearest centimeter.
- Resting Heart Rate: The resting heart rate was measured in beats per minute, bpm, after the subject had been comfortably seated at rest for a sufficient period.

Data Collection

The data collection was done in two phases. Pre-test measurement from both Experimental and Control Groups was obtained before the initiation of Suryanamaskar training program. Similarly, post-test measurements were taken after completing the six-month training period. All the tests were conducted under similar environmental conditions.

Statistical Analysis

The data thus collected were subjected to statistical treatment, wherever appropriate. Means and standard deviation were computed for both the groups at pre-test and post-test stages. The t-test was used to ascertain the significance of difference between pre-test and post-test means. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

Data Analysis

The following statistical procedures were used for the analysis of data:

- Calculation of Mean
- Calculation of SD
- Calculation of SED - Standard Error of Difference
- Calculation of Standard Error of Mean (SEM)

Calculation of t-ratio Calculated t-values were compared with tabulated t-value at 0.05 level of significance to decide the statistical significance of observed differences.

Results

The findings of the current study can be used to assess the impact of six months of Suryanamaskar exercise training on certain motor fitness and physiological factors such as standing broad jump and heart rate of school-going children of Delhi. The data from the Experimental Groups and the Control Groups, both pre-tested (0th month) and post-tested (6th month) conditions, were statistically analyzed with the help of the calculation of the Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Difference (SED), Standard Error of Mean (SEM), and t-ratio. The significance criterion was set at 0.05.

Table-01(Experimental Group)

Variables	Subjects	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	SEM
Standing Broad Jump (m)	Pre	1.30	0.27	0.085	5.37	0.06
	Post	1.76	0.26			
Resting Heart Rate (bpm)	Pre	94.00	10.50	1.65	6.67	1.17
	Post	83.00	8.00			

*Significantat0.05level

SD = Standard Deviation, SED = Standard Error of Difference, SEM = Standard Error of Mean

Table-02(Control Group)

Variables	Subjects	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	SEM
Standing Broad Jump (m)	Pre	1.38	0.20	0.077	1.98	0.05
	Post	1.53	0.28			
Resting Heart Rate (bpm)	Pre	96.50	16.00	1.20	0.42	0.85
	Post	97.00	15.50			

SD = Standard Deviation, SED = Standard Error of Difference, SEM = Standard Error of Mean

Interpretation of Results

From Table – 01, it is testified that there is a significant improvement in the performance of standing broad jump and a significant decrease in the resting heart rate by the Experimental group after six months of Suryanamaskar exercise, as the value of t-ratio is significant at the 0.05 level. The increased value in standing broad jump performance depicts that there is increased muscle strength, while the reduced value of resting heart rate portrays efficiency.

It has been found from Table-02 that the Control Group did not exhibit statistically significance difference in terms of performance in standing broad jump along with resting heart rate. The calculated t-ratio values were not significant, which means that the usual school schedule was not able to produce a positive result in the selected variables.

Therefore, it was clear from the above findings that the six months systematic Suryanamaskar practice had a significant positive impact on the muscular strength and cardiovascular efficiency of school-going children of Delhi.

Discussion

The present study was undertaken to assess the effect of six months of systematic Suryanamaskar training on selected motor fitness and physiological variables, namely standing broad jump and resting heart rate, of school-going students of Delhi. The results of the present study, as are evident in the Results section, conclusively state that the Experimental Group had demonstrated statistically significant improvements for both the variables, while the Control Group did not register any significant changes during the same period. Now, within the subsequent discussion of the results is done in a tabular manner, strictly adhering to the interpretations that have been provided in the thesis, variable-wise.

Effect of Suryanamaskar Training on Standing Broad Jump

The performance of the Standing broad jump improved significantly in the Experimental Group after six months of training in Suryanamaskar. Increased mean jump distance indicated an improvement in the explosive muscular strength of lower extremities. The standing broad jump is considered a better index of leg power and neuromuscular coordination, so its improvement can be assumed to be a positive adaptation of the musculoskeletal system because of regular training.

Suryanamaskar is dynamic in nature, comprising weight-bearing activities repeatedly, forward and backward bending, and continuous transitions between postures. The muscles of the lower limbs, including quadriceps, hamstrings, gluteal muscles, and calf muscles, undergo stresses all the time during the execution of movements. With a protracted training period, repetitive muscular engagement of this nature can lead to an increase in force-generating capacity and increased neuromuscular coordination between muscle groups, leading to increased performance in the standing broad jump, denoting explosive power.

The Control Group improved only marginally in standing broad jump performance; this improvement was not statistically significant. This in itself suggests that either routine activities at school and normal physical education classes were inadequate to bring out worthwhile improvements in muscular strength, or the sampling was from a group where such improvement

does not easily take place. The significant 'F' value between Experimental and Control Groups ensures that the improvement in standing broad jump performance was mainly due to this structured Suryanamaskar training programme.

Effect of Suryanamaskar Training on Resting Heart Rate

Resting heart rate was significantly lower in the Experimental Group after six months of Suryanamaskar training. A lowered resting heart rate has traditionally been used as an indicator of improved cardiovascular efficiency and increased functional capacity of the heart. Regular aerobic exercise has been shown to produce several long-term adaptations that include increased stroke volume and decreased cardiac workload under conditions of rest, which contribute to a lower resting heart rate.

Suryanamaskar consists of continuous physical movement combined with regulated breathing patterns. Such coordinated activity may facilitate improved autonomic regulation and cardiovascular adaptation over time. The significant reduction in resting heart rate observed in the Experimental Group therefore suggests that regular Suryanamaskar practice positively influenced cardiac efficiency and overall physiological regulation among the subjects.

On the other hand, at similar intervals, the Control Group did not show any significant fluctuation in resting heart rate for a period of six months. This clearly suggests that routine daily activities and unstructured physical movements are not enough to bring about any meaningful cardiovascular changes. The absence of significant alteration in the Control Group further establishes evidence of Suryanamaskar being effective as a structured intervention for training in cardiovascular efficiency.

Overall Interpretation of Findings

Taken together, the above findings of the present study indicate quite conclusively that six months of consistent and systematic Suryanamaskar training brought about marked improvements in muscular strength, as reflected by standing broad jump performance, and in cardiovascular efficiency as reflected by resting heart rate. The absence of significant changes in the Control Group ensures that these improvements are not due to natural growth, maturation, or routine school activities, but were a result as a consequence of the Suryanamaskar training programme. These findings are in concert with the interpretations raised in the thesis, underlining the role of structured yogic practices in enhancing motor fitness and physiological efficiency. The comprehensiveness of Suryanamaskar makes it an effective and practical kind of exercise because it incorporates dynamic physical movement with controlled breathing, thus improving many aspects of physical fitness simultaneously. Overall, the findings are supportive of including Suryanamaskar as a regular feature of the school-based physical education program in order to improve muscular strength and cardiovascular efficiency among urban school-going adolescents due to limited opportunities in structured physical activities.

Conclusion

On the basis of the results obtained from the current study, it can be concluded that the six months organized Suryanamaskar practice has a significant positive impact on the selected variables of motor fitness and physiological parameters among the school-going children of Delhi. The Experimental Group, which followed organized Suryanamaskar practice, showed significant improvement in the performance of standing broad jump and significant decrease in resting heart rate, whereas the Control Group did not show significant changes in these variables.

The marked improvement found in the performance of standing broad jump has revealed an increase in the strength and explosive power of the lower limbs in the students undergoing Suryanamaskar training. The decline in the resting heart rate of the Experimental Group has indicated an improvement in the cardiac efficiency of the students, which reveals that the practice of Suryanamaskar helps increase the efficiency of the heart.

The fact that there have not been any significant modifications in the Control Group affirms the fact that the normal school activities were not enough to bring about effective modifications in the strength of muscles and the efficiency of the cardiovascular system. This clearly reveals the fact that the modifications occurred in the Experimental Group were a direct result of the Suryanamaskar training program.

It is evident from the results of the present study that the effectiveness of Suryanamaskar as a simple and economical form of physical exercise to be included as a part of the physical education program of schools is highly successful. It is evident from the results of the present study that the space and equipment needed to perform Suryanamaskar is very minimal, and hence, it is highly suitable to be performed in schools. Therefore, the results of the present study support the concept of using Suryanamaskar as a regular training program to enhance the muscle and physiological health of the school-going children.

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